

Practical Inverse Rendering of Textured and Translucent Appearance: Supplemental document

1 NORMAL MAPPING IMPLEMENTATION

The normal map optimization requires careful handling of invalid, backfacing normals. We employ Schüssler et al. [2017]’s normal map flipping strategy to ensure frontfacing normals during rendering. Importantly, this approach does not introduce additional discontinuities. Since normals are interpolated continuously, there is a smooth transition between frontfacing orientations, those orthogonal to the view direction, and backfacing orientations, where flipping is activated. We did not to implement any energy-loss compensation [Schüssler et al. 2017], as it would significantly increase rendering costs. However, energy loss can be partially mitigated through the joint optimization of the albedo texture. Furthermore, we implemented the shadow terminator fix proposed by Estevez et al. [2019], which we found to effectively prevent artifacts at shadow boundaries.

2 PYRAMID REPRESENTATION AS GRADIENT FILTERING

We here provide an explicit formulation of the equivalence between a pyramid representation and linear gradient filtering discussed in the main text’s Figure 4. We use a two-level pyramid and denote by $\boldsymbol{\pi} = \{\boldsymbol{\pi}_0, \boldsymbol{\pi}_1\}$ its Laplacian pyramid levels. Nearest-neighbor upsampling and box-filtered downsampling by an integer factor s are represented as functions $u(\cdot)$ and $d(\cdot)$. We write the final image I as the accumulation of the two pyramid levels, where the lower-resolution level is upsampled to the final resolution:

$$I(\boldsymbol{\pi}) = \boldsymbol{\pi}_0 + u(\boldsymbol{\pi}_1). \quad (1)$$

Given a two-level image pyramid, we can compute the parameter derivative of an objective function $g(I(\boldsymbol{\pi}))$ as:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \frac{\partial I}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \left(\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_0}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_0} + \frac{\partial u(\boldsymbol{\pi}_1)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_1} \right). \quad (2)$$

Therefore, we get the following expressions for the gradients w.r.t. $\boldsymbol{\pi}_0$ and $\boldsymbol{\pi}_1$:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_0} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_1} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \frac{\partial u(\boldsymbol{\pi}_1)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}_1} = s^2 d \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \right), \quad (4)$$

where the last equality directly follows from the definition of the used up- and downsampling operators (i.e., the Jacobian of the up-sampling operator is the downsampling operator multiplied by s^2). Since both gradients are a linear function of $\frac{\partial g}{\partial I}$, and the accumulation of the pyramid levels to form the final image is also a linear operation, it follows that the overall update to the final image I is a linear operation of the image gradient too:

$$F \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \right) = \frac{\partial g}{\partial I} + u \left(s^2 d \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial I} \right) \right). \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. We compare our method to the Laplacian preconditioner of Nicolet et al. [2021] on a scene where a 4096^2 texture is simultaneously optimized for a close-up (top row) and a wide-angle view (bottom row), each rendered at 1024^2 . We find the optimal learning rate and smoothing weight λ using a grid search. We do this for both views at the same time (“Opt. combined”), as well as for each view individually (“Opt. close” and “Opt. far”). No single smoothing factor λ works well for both views simultaneously.

If we use standard gradient descent without momentum, it is therefore equivalent to update a two-level pyramid, or to just filter the image gradient using the linear filter F .

3 LAPLACIAN PRECONDITIONER LIMITATION

In Fig. 1, we provide a comparison against the Laplacian preconditioner [Nicolet et al. 2021] using an identical setup as the one presented in Figure 5 of the main paper. Their approach suffers from the same limitation as the cross-bilateral gradient filtering [Chang et al. 2024] and it is hard to find an optimal smoothing parameter λ .

4 COMPARISON WITH DENG ET. AL : OPTIMIZATION SETUP

We further describe the optimization setup used in Figure 13 of the paper for both our approach and the method of Deng et al. [2022] (see also Figure 6 in their paper). They propose to optimize albedo and roughness maps at 512^2 resolution as well as a scalar index of refraction and spectrally-varying extinction coefficient. We instead optimize textured (and spectrally-varying) anisotropy of a Heney-Greenstein (HG) phase function (512^2), albedo (2048^2) and spectrally-varying extinction (RGB vector). For the boundary BSDF, we found that using a principled BSDF, for which we optimize clearcoat, roughness and normal maps, all at a 2048^2 resolution, gives the best result. Their implementation uses 1 randomly sampled view per iteration and a 2-scale texture optimization, 10^6 000

Fig. 2. The key distinction between the first and second rows lies in the subsurface scattering model used. Our path-traced differentiable subsurface scattering yields more apparent translucent effects, even with a simplified principled BSDF model where only roughness was optimized. Finally, using our Laplacian mipmapping and optimizing clearcoat as well as normal map parameters improve the recovery of high frequency details, closing the gap to the reference further.

iterations at texture resolution 256^2 and another 10^4 iteration at 512^2 . We then select the optimized parameters with lowest error (achieved at iteration 16850 with their method). Our optimization, on the other hand, runs for 4096 iterations but randomly samples 4 views at every iterations to achieve similar number of gradient steps. We keep the parameters of the last optimization step for our final results. In the second row of Fig. 2, we additionally present the result of our optimization without Laplacian mipmapping and a simplified principled BSDF model. We only optimize the textured roughness and subsurface scattering parameters, all at resolution 512^2 , demonstrating the benefit of the path-traced subsurface compared to the differentiable dipole model of Deng et al. [2022].

5 SUBSURFACE SCATTERING GRADIENTS : PHASE FUNCTION

While Algorithm 2 in the paper does not account for the phase function parameter gradients, we show in Algorithm 1 that adding support for them is simple and still only requires a single differentiable texture fetch operation, similarly to the other subsurface parameters. Assuming a Henyey-Greenstein phase function with anisotropy parameter g we propose to “manually” accumulate gradients with respect to the phase function at every iteration of the volume sampling loop. We achieve this via a forward gradient pass

```

1 def accumulate_subsurface_scattering_gradient( $\delta_L, L, \dots$ ):
2    $N = 0, \hat{t} = 0.0$ 
3    $x_{\text{surface}} = \text{ray\_intersect}(\text{ray}, \dots)$ 
4
5    $\sigma, \rho, g, \dots = \text{evaluate\_volume\_parameters}(x_{\text{surface}}, \pi, \dots)$ 
6    $g_{\text{local}} = \text{detach}(g)$ 
7   while current path in scattering medium:
8      $t, T = \text{sample\_transmittance}(\sigma, \dots)$ 
9      $\omega_i = \text{sample\_phase\_function}(\text{ray}, \dots)$ 
10     $\beta_i = \rho * \sigma * T$ 
11     $\hat{t} += t$ 
12     $N += 1$ 
13
14    # Accumulate phase function derivative w.r.t. local g param
15    set_grad( $g_{\text{local}}, 1$ )
16     $f_p = \text{eval\_phase\_function}(g_{\text{local}}, \omega_o, \text{ray})$ 
17     $\delta_g += \text{forward}(f_p / \text{detach}(f_p))$ 
18    ...
19
20  $\delta_\pi += \text{backward}(\delta_L * L * (N * \rho * \sigma / \text{detach}(\rho * \sigma) - \hat{t} * \sigma)$ 
21     $* g * \text{detach}(\delta_g))$ 
22 ...

```

Algorithm 1. Pseudocode for the modified PRB with support for differentiable phase function parameters.

Fig. 3. The albedo remapping we use provides a decent initialization for the subsurface scattering parameters, but further optimization is critical for accurate recovery of the skin appearance.

restricted to the phase function and a *local* g parameter which does *not* track derivatives with respect to the texture fetches (Lines 14-17). After the volume sampling loop, we then take the product of the accumulated gradient with the texture parameter g to account for derivatives with respect to the texture fetch and perform the backward pass to propagate all derivatives (Lines 20-21).

6 FACIAL APPEARANCE CAPTURE

6.1 Optimization settings

We provide detailed optimization settings for our facial appearance reconstruction.

Phase I. In the first phase, we optimize the parameters of a principled BSDF [Burley 2012] without subsurface scattering. We use the following settings

- **Number of iterations:** 136
- **Multiresolution optimization:** We start by rendering 16×24 resolution, and increase render resolution to 2048×3072 in 8 steps using an exponential schedule (i.e., each resolution gets twice the iteration count of the previous one).
- **Render settings:** We use path replay backpropagation with a maximum depth of 3. We use 32 samples per pixel (SPP) for the primal image and 4 SPP for the gradient.
- **Data:** We use all 13 cameras and 14 lights in every iteration (for a total of 182 renderings).
- **Loss function:** Huber loss with $\delta = 4.0$.
- **BSDF parameters:** We optimize a 4096^2 normal map, 2048^2 albedo, 512^2 roughness, 256^2 displacement map and use a fixed IOR of 1.5.
- **Learning rates:** normal map: 0.0025, roughness: 0.005, base color: 0.0025, displacement: 0.0005
- **Initialization:** normal map: unit vector, roughness: 0.4, albedo: average projected color from the full-on images, displacement: 0.0.

Note that Mitsuba does not support per-ray displacement map mipmapping. We therefore revert to globally selecting the mipmap resolution that is appropriate for the current render resolution.

Phase II. In the second phase, we keep normal map, roughness and displacement fixed and use the following settings to fit the subsurface scattering parameters:

- **Number of iterations:** 136
- **Multiresolution optimization:** We start by rendering 16×24 resolution, and increase render resolution to 2048×3072 using the same exponential schedule as in phase I.
- **Render settings:** Our volume PRB with ray differentials and max surface depth 4, max sss depth=512. We use 32 samples per pixel for the primal image and 4 SPP for the gradient.
- **Data:** 8 randomly sampled light/camera configs from the 14 lights x 13 cameras at every iteration. We found this to be sufficient, as subsurface scattering parameters are less high frequency than the specular highlights we recover in phase I.
- **Loss function:** Relative L_2 error.
- **BSDF parameters:** Principled BSDF (with diffuse exit) and textured (remapped) sss albedo at 2048^2 , extinction and HG anisotropy parameter both at 128^2
- **Learning rates:** SSS albedo: 0.0025, extinction: 50.0, HG: 0.001.
- **Initialization:** SSS albedo: remapped from optimized albedo from phase I, extinction: [1000.0,1000.0,1000.0], HG anisotropy g : [0.0,0.0,0.0].

In Fig. 3 we show the initial state of the subsurface scattering optimization (rendered at the final resolution).

6.2 Additional results

See Fig. 4, Fig. 5, Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 for additional facial appearance capture results.

REFERENCES

Brent Burley. 2012. Physically-based shading at Disney. *SIGGRAPH Course Notes. Practical physically-based shading in film and game production.* (2012), 1–27.

- Wesley Chang, Xuanda Yang, Yash Belhe, Ravi Ramamoorthi, and Tzu-Mao Li. 2024. Spatiotemporal Bilateral Gradient Filtering for Inverse Rendering. In *SIGGRAPH Asia Conference Papers*. ACM, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3680528.3687606>
- Xi Deng, Fujun Luan, Bruce Walter, Kavita Bala, and Steve Marschner. 2022. Reconstructing Translucent Objects Using Differentiable Rendering. In *SIGGRAPH Conference Papers*. Article 38, 10 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3528233.3530714>
- Alejandro Conty Estevez, Pascal Lecocq, and Clifford Stein. 2019. *A Microfacet-Based Shadowing Function to Solve the Bump Terminator Problem*. Apress. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4842-4427-2_12
- Baptiste Nicolet, Alec Jacobson, and Wenzel Jakob. 2021. Large Steps in Inverse Rendering of Geometry. *ACM Trans. Graph. (Proc. SIGGRAPH Asia)* 40, 6 (Dec. 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3478513.3480501>
- Vincent Schüssler, Eric Heitz, Johannes Hanika, and Carsten Dachsbacher. 2017. Microfacet-based normal mapping for robust Monte Carlo path tracing. *ACM Trans. Graph. (Proc. SIGGRAPH Asia)* 36, 6, Article 205 (Nov. 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3130800.3130806>

Fig. 4. Skin reconstruction for multiple camera and lights.

Fig. 5. Skin reconstruction for multiple camera and lights.

Fig. 6. Skin reconstruction for multiple camera and lights.

Fig. 7. Skin reconstruction for multiple camera and lights.

Fig. 8. Skin reconstruction for multiple camera and lights.